

Assessing Relative Efficiency of Islamic Banks in Bahrain: An Application of Data Envelopment Analysis

Author's Details

⁽¹⁾Prof. Minwir Al-Shammari. College of Business Administration University of Bahrain ⁽²⁾Dr. Seref Turen. College of Business Administration University of Bahrain

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to measure the comparative operating efficiency of retail Islamic banks operating in the Kingdom of Bahrain over the sample period 2010-2013. The study employed Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) model as a non-parametric multi-criteria methodology for assessing relative efficiency of Decision-Making Units (DMUs). The variables considered are the financial information gathered from the financial statements issued by the investigated banks. The paper computes banks technical, pure technical, and scale efficiency scores, areas of efficiency improvements, and composite reference sets of the relatively inefficient banks.

Keywords: Bahrain, Islamic Banks, Data Envelopment Analysis Technical Efficiency, Pure technical efficiency, and Scale Efficiency

Introduction

Inherently, banks and the banking sector especially in developing countries play a vital role in the economy. Therefore, many studies suggest that the efficiency of banks directly affects national economic growth. As to the Islamic banking and finance, in global terms, is still relatively small part of the global financial system but it is one which is growing rapidly thanks to openness to all and not restricted to Muslims only. As it is well known, operations of Islamic financial institutions are predominantly based on a profit and loss sharing principle. An Islamic bank does not charge interest yet participates in yield stemming from usage of the funds whereas its account holder shares profit of the bank in accordance with a predetermined ratio because of partnership between the Islamic bank and its account holder. Hence, Islamic finance particularly concentrates on the transaction and it gives room all types of institutions if Islamic or conventional to participate in as long as the underlying transaction and asset is Sharia'a (Islamic Law) compliant.

The study aims to measure the technical, pure technical, and scale efficiency scores of Islamic banks in Bahrain over the period of 2010-2013 using a non-parametric multi-criteria methodology known as Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). Furthermore, it seeks to find banks' areas of efficiency improvement and best reference sets. The rest of the study is organized as follows: brief review of the Islamic banking sector in Bahrain, review of related literature, the DEA models, methodology of the study, empirical findings, and concluding remarks.

Islamic Banking Sector in Bahrain

The name Bahrain means "two seas" in Arabic, referring to the seas that surround the Gulf island nation. Bahrain is home to the great deal of Islamic financial institutions in the Middle East. According to the report by Oxford Business Group (2012), the sector contributed \$25.4 billion USD, and its market share in total banking assets rose from 1.8% in 2000 to 13.3% in 2012. In addition, Bahrain also hosts some regulatory authorities which provide international standards for the sector, such as Islamic International Rating Agency, International Islamic Financial Market, General Counsel for Islamic Banks and Institutions and Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions.

As one of the world's leading centers for Islamic finance, the birth of the sector dates back to 1978 when Bahrain Islamic Bank was set up. Islamic banking in the Kingdom of Bahrain gained momentum in the early 1980s with the issue of 4 licenses; one was an offshore banking unit whereas remainders were investment banking licenses. During the 1990s, a total of 8 licenses were issued to institutions seeking to pursue Islamic banking services. The Kingdom has a strong Islamic finance infrastructure in place together with her 26 Islamic bank licenses, 7 Islamic insurance so-called *Takaful* companies and 2 re-*takaful* companies operating in the country when it is considered that Islamic finance in its modern form is a relatively young industry.

DEA for Assessing Efficiency of Islamic Banks

The concept of efficiency is generally referred to as the ratio of input elements used by a production organization to its production output. Relative efficiency is a concept proposed by Farrell (1957) to measure technical efficiency (TE) of production units through comparison

with composite unit, or reference set, which has similar input and output structure.

DEA is a linear programming model to assess relative efficiency of decision-making units (DMUs) that use multiple incommensurable input and multiple incommensurable output measures. DEA assesses efficiency by estimating a production frontier boundary based on input or output orientation. That is, the performance of each DMU is measured relative to the performance of all other DMUs. The relative efficiency of a DMU is defined as the ratio of the sum of its weighted outputs, to the sum of its weighted inputs. The DMU being evaluated can be judged relatively inefficient if the composite unit requires less input to obtain the output achieved by the unit being evaluated, or judged relatively efficient if the composite unit requires at least the same amount of input as the unit being evaluated.

A large part of existing literature examines the efficiency of Islamic banks. A summary of previous studies on the efficiency of Islamic Banks is compiled in Table 1. Said (2013) measures overall technical efficiency of Islamic banks operating in the MENA region by employing DEA during the financial crisis of 2007-2009. He finds

out that the Islamic banks of the region on average are technically inefficient. In addition, the decomposition of technical efficiency as pure and scale shows that examined banks have problems in the allocation of resources between their inputs and outputs mix compared to Islamic banks operating in GCC countries.

Zainal and Ismail (2012) examine the efficiency of 17 Islamic banks operating in Malaysia by using DEA considering total deposits, personal expenses and fixed assets as inputs and total financing and advances and together with other earning assets as output for the period of 2006 and 2010. The research reveals that the local Islamic banks scored higher technical and scale efficiency than those of foreign owned Islamic banks. Yet, foreign owned Islamic banks are better in terms of pure technical efficiency.

Noor and Ahmad (2012) examine the efficiency of Islamic banking sector in 25 countries with 78 examples including Bahrain, Bangladesh, Brunei, Egypt, Gambia, Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Malaysia, Mauritania, Pakistan, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Syria, Thailand, Turkey, UAE, Qatar, UK, South Africa, Sudan and Yemen, during the period 1992-2009. Findings show that a

Table 1: Summary of previous DEA studies on the efficiency of Islamic banks

AUTHOR	OBSERVATION PERIOD	COUNTRIES ANALYZED	INPUTS	OUTPUTS
Said (2013)	2007-2009	MENA Countries	Labor Cost Fixed Asset T. Deposits	T. Loans Liquid Assets Other Income
Zainal and Ismail (2012)	2006-2010	Malaysia	T. Deposits Personal Expenses Fixed Assets	T. Loans Other Earning Assets
Noor and Ahmed (2012)	1992-2009	25 Different Countries	T. Deposits Labor Cost T. Assets	T. Loans Income Other Earning Assets
Abu-Alkheil et.al (2012)	2005-2008	UK	T. Deposits and short term funding T. Expenses T. Staff Cost	T. Loans T. Revenues
Pramuka (2011)	2003-2009	Indonesia	T. Deposits Overhead Expenses Physical Capital	Profit Before tax and financing
Moussawi and Obeid (2011)	2005-2008	GCC Countries	T. Earning Assets Commission Revenues T. Deposits Fixed Assets	Interest Expense Personnel Expenses Other Operating Expenses
Mostafa (2011)	2009	100 Islamic banks of the World	T. Assets Equity	Net Income ROA ROE
Onour and Abdulla (2011)	2007-2008	Sudan	Salaries and Wages T. Deposits	Net Loans Net Income
Mostafa (2007)	2005	GCC Countries	T. Assets Capital	Net Profit ROA ROE
Sufian (2007)	2001-2005	Malaysia	T. Deposits Loan Loss Provisions	T. Loans Investments
Sufian (2006)	2001-2004	Malaysia	T. Deposits Labor Expenses T. Assets	T. Loans Income
Yudistira (2004)	1997-2000	In and out of Middle East	Staff Costs Fixed Assets T. Deposits	T. Loans Other Income Liquid Assets

positive relationship exists between bank efficiency and size and profitability, while a negative relationship exists between bank efficiency and loan intensity and capitalization. In addition to this pure technical efficiency has greater influence in determining the total technical inefficiency of the world Islamic banking sector.

Abu-Alkheil et al (2012) investigate the relative efficiency of Islamic Bank of Britain by applying two-stage DEA to determine the impact of internal and external factors on bank's efficiency over the period

from 2005 to 2008. The results indicate that the Islamic Bank of Britain is technically inefficient. It has also relatively poor financial performance that bank's inefficiency results in both size and management issues.

Pramuka (2011) provides empirical evidence of Islamic bank efficiency in Indonesia using stochastic frontier approach over the period 2003 and 2009. He finds that full-fledged banks are more efficient in making profit compared to Islamic windows. Therefore, Islamic banks should focus on making loan to the industry rather than investing in financial markets.

Moussawi and Obeid (2011) investigate the productive performance of Islamic banks of the GCC countries during 2005-2008. DEA is used to decompose the productive efficiency into technical efficiency, allocation efficiency and cost efficiency for a sample of 23 Islamic banks. The findings reveal that the technical inefficiency and allocation inefficiency increase bank costs by about 14% and 29%, respectively.

Mostafa (2011) attempted to measure the relative efficiency of top 100 Islamic banks in the world through DEA by using cross-sectional data for the year 2009. He points out that the performance of several banks were sub-optimal which means that there are potential for significant improvements. He emphasizes on the asset mismanagement in certain banks where considerable scope for reduction of those assets is.

Onour and Abdalla (2011) analyze 12 Islamic banks in Sudan for 2007 and 2008 to determine the efficiency using DEA. They find that only 2 banks in the sample score technical efficiency level whereas smallest banks score pure technical efficiency but are scale inefficient. They suggest this result as evidence that government and private ownership is not a constraint of managerial and scale efficiency but bank's size is important factor for scale efficiency.

Mostafa (2007) examines the relative efficiency of the top 50 banks in GCC region using DEA to the cross-sectional data for the year 2005. The results indicate that the performance of several banks is sub-optimal, indicating the potential for significant improvement.

Sufian (2007) measure the performance of 17 Islamic banks of Malaysian Banking sector during the period of 2001-2005. Several efficiency estimates of individual banks are calculated using DEA method. Risk factor is included by incorporating problem loans as non-discretionary input variable. He finds out that scale inefficiency dominates pure technical inefficiency in the Islamic banking sector of Malaysia. Besides, foreign banks exhibit higher technical efficiency than domestic peers.

Sufian (2006) works on Malaysian Islamic banking sector for the period of 2001 and 2004 by using DEA. The intermediation approach is applied to the specification of input-output variables. He observes that the scale inefficiency dominates pure technical inefficiency in the sector which means that the banks are operating at the wrong scale of operations. Besides, domestic Islamic banks shows higher technical

efficiency compared to that of their foreign peers whereas foreign ones are relatively more efficient in controlling their operating costs.

Yudistira (2004) test the stability and efficiency of 18 Islamic banks from in and out of Middle Eastern countries for the period of 1997 to 2000. In this study, technical, pure technical and scale efficiency measures are computed through non-parametric DEA. Findings show that the overall efficiency results suggest that inefficiency is over 10 % which can be considered quite low compared to many commercial banks. Islamic banks suffered from the crisis of 1989-1999 but recovered very well after those turbulent times. In addition, small and medium sized Islamic banks exhibit diseconomies of scale.

DEA Models

DEA basic models are two types: CCR model of Charnes, Cooper and Rhodes (1978) and BCC Model of Banker, Charnes and Cooper (1984).

CCR Model

The CCR model is a fractional and nonlinear model that includes multiple incommensurable inputs and multiple incommensurable outputs based on the assumption of constant returns to scale (CRS), viz. scale of economies does not change as size of the service facility increases. The CCR fractional and nonlinear DEA model can be solved by one of two linear programming formulations. The first formulation, which had output-orientation, maximizes the ratio of weighted multiple outputs to weighted multiple inputs and constrains the weighted sum of inputs to be unity. In output-oriented formulation, attention is focused on augmenting outputs for a given available level of inputs to increase efficiency. The second formulation, which had input-oriented, is the dual of the first model and its attention is focused on reducing inputs given certain level of outputs to increase efficiency.. In input-oriented formulation, managers are assumed to have more control over the inputs rather than outputs.

BBC Model

The BBC model differs from the CCR model only in addressing the impact of economy of scale on relative efficiency, by adding a new assumption of returns to scale (RTS), viz. variable returns to scale (VRS) which is divided into these two types (Kumar and Gulati, 2008):

- Increasing returns to scale (IRS): it implies that an increase in size of service operations

increases DMU efficiency. For example, a bank is assumed to be too small for its scale of operations and an increase in size leads to improvement in efficiency.

- Decreasing returns to scale (DRS): it implies that a reduction in scale of production increases efficiency, then, there is no efficiency gain by increasing the scale of production. Inappropriate size of a DMU (small or large) may sometimes be a cause for technical inefficiency. For example, a bank is assumed to be too large for the volume of activities that it conducts and a reduction in size of its service operations improves its efficiency.

Efficiency of DMUs may result from factors such as the best utilization of resources; scale of the production process, prices of inputs, etc. Major types of efficiency evaluations of DMUs can be divided into three types (Kumar and Gulati, 2008):

- Overall technical efficiency (TE): it is used to measure input-oriented or output-oriented efficiency under the CRS assumption.
- Pure technical efficiency (PTE): it is derived from the BCC model to measure efficiency under the VRS assumption that is due to managerial intervention in organizing the bank's inputs, and
- Scale efficiency (SE): it is the ratio of TE to PTE.

DEA Efficiency Evaluations

Methodology and Data Description

Model

The adopted input-oriented DEA model represents the dual of the output-oriented linear programming formulation. The objective function of the adopted DEA model is to minimize the relative efficiency score and the linear programming formulation is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min } Z &= \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_j x_i \\ \text{s.t. } \quad &\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_j x_{ij} \leq x_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n); \\ &\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_j y_{rj} \geq y_{r0} \quad (r = 1, 2, \dots, m); \\ &\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_j = 1; \\ &\lambda_j \geq 0 \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, N). \end{aligned}$$

where the following notation is used:

Z: efficiency score;

λ_j : weights attached to inputs and outputs of bank j;

X_i : inputs and outputs of the particular bank whose efficiency is being evaluated.

X_{ij} : observed value of input i for bank j;

Y_{rj} : observed value of output r for bank j;

Data

The population of the study represents six retail Islamic banks in Bahrain. Therefore, the study uses a total population sampling. The selected banks, viz. Decision-Making Units (DMUs), were as follows:

- DMU1 = Al-Baraka Islamic Bank
- DMU2 = Al-Salam Bank
- DMU3 = Bahrain Islamic Bank
- DMU4 = Ithmar Bank
- DMU5 = Khaleeji Commercial Bank

- DMU6 = Kuwait Finance House

The input measures were total assets and total owner's equity whereas the output measures were total operating income and net profit (loss). Banking data were gathered from web sites of the banks. The total number of inputs and outputs has been planned not to exceed the number of DMUs as suggested by Charnes *et al.* (1994) in order to discriminate between efficient and inefficient banks. The input and output data used in the study represents six Bahraini Islamic banks over the period 2010-2013 (Table 2).

Table 2: Input and output data for the years 2010-2013 (Figures in Million BDs)

		Inputs		Outputs		
		Total Assets	Total Owner's Equity	Total Operating Income	Net Profit (Loss)	Adjusted Net Profit (Loss)
2010	DMU1	5,987.5	685.0	248.3	1.7	3.48
	DMU2	856.6	201.9	22.4	7.3	14.66
	DMU3	935.600	100.600	17.300	-39.700	0.23
	DMU4	2,543.700	247.500	85.050	-52.700	0.30
	DMU5	419.200	118.100	12.500	-6.500	0.04
	DMU6	1,446.600	360.200	75.600	9.300	18.65
2011	DMU1	6468	678.4	279.4	0.980	1.99
	DMU2	923.9	200.6	12.7	0.5	0.99
	DMU3	839.100	101.300	26.100	-17.300	0.52
	DMU4	2601.100	217.400	65.900	-23.300	0.70
	DMU5	447.500	118.900	14.700	0.518	1.05
	DMU6	1,537.300	372.900	77.000	9.600	19.49
2012	DMU1	534.7	63.6	15.40	-4.0	0.10
	DMU2	942.00	208.10	23.10	10.30	20.86
	DMU3	832.800	69.700	24.400	-36.100	0.90
	DMU4	2,724.100	222.100	87.500	-10.100	0.25
	DMU5	473.100	119.400	10.600	0.751	1.52
	DMU6	1,437.000	381.800	60.300	8.700	17.62
2013	DMU1	614.9	62.1	16.4	0.34	0.69
	DMU2	1,088.00	246.10	26.10	12.40	25.23
	DMU3	910.200	78.100	36.900	6.100	12.41
	DMU4	2,790.900	200.400	75.300	-29.900	1.03
	DMU5	542.200	100.010	7.000	-19.000	0.66
	DMU6	1,565.000	367.700	53.100	5.800	11.80

As the basic DEA model requires all numbers to be non-negative and preferably strictly positive (no zero values), many data sets that include negative numbers have been revised. Negative net income and net profit have been revised to positive values and, accordingly, other data sets have been proportionally adjusted. Furthermore, and in order to unify the currency value for all measures used, values expressed in US dollars were converted into Bahraini Dinars (BD) where 1 BD = US \$ 0.377.

Empirical Findings and Discussion

In analyzing the data, The DEA model was run twice, once under the CRS assumption and then under the variable returns to scale (VRS) assumption with input orientation option. Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation) of the selected input and output variables for the Islamic banks over the period 2010-2013.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables Employed in the Model (Minimum, Maximum, and Mean Figures in Million BDs)

Name	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
2010				
Total Assets	419.2	5,987.5	2,031.5	2,070.5
Total Owner's Equity	100.6	685.0	285.6	217.2
Total Operating Income	12.5	248.3	76.9	89.6
Adjusted Net Profit (Loss)	0.04	18.65	6.2	8.3
2011				
Total Assets	447.5	101.3	2136.2	2,251.4
Total Owner's Equity	101.3	678.4	281.6	217.0
Total Operating Income	2136.2	281.6	79.3	101.7
Adjusted Net Profit (Loss)	2251.4	217.0	4.1	7.5
2012				
Total Assets	473.1	2,724.1	1,157.3	841.5
Total Owner's Equity	63.6	381.8	177.5	120.5
Total Operating Income	10.6	87.5	36.9	30.4
Adjusted Net Profit (Loss)	0.1	20.9	6.9	9.6
2013				
Total Assets	542.2	2,790.9	1,251.9	839.0
Total Owner's Equity	62.1	367.7	175.7	118.8
Total Operating Income	7.0	75.3	35.8	25.1
Adjusted Net Profit (Loss)	0.66	25.2	8.6	9.8

Technical, Pure Technical, and Scale Efficiencies

Using the preceding DEA model and data for the 6 Bahraini Islamic banks, TE, PTE and SE annual scores as well as means and standard deviations are calculated for the period from 2010 to 2013 and reported in Tables 4-6.

The CRS assumption is applied in measuring TE of DMUs wherein there is no significant relationship between the DMU's scale of operations and its efficiency. As shown in Table 4, the number of fully efficient Islamic banks as per TE was three in 2010 and 2012 and two in 2011 and 2013. The TE scores presented high standard deviations. The DMUs showed high dispersion in terms of TE scores. The mean TE score was 83 percent in 2010 but dropped to 73 percent in

2011 and increased to 80 percent in 2012 but dropped to 77 percent in 2013. The average TE scores of suggest that the Islamic Banking sector in Bahrain is highly efficient as overall. The low number of fully efficient Islamic banks means that there is a large room for improvement.

The PTE measurement adopts the VRS assumption after eliminating the scale inefficiency by dividing the TE score by the PTE score. Table 5 showed that the number of fully PTE banks was 6 in 2010 and 2013, 4 in 2011, and 5 in 2012. The PTE scores presented high standard deviations for 3 DMUS and zero for the rest of DMUs. The mean PTE score that was 100 percent in 2010 but dropped to 91 percent in 2011 and increased to 94 percent in 2012 and reached 100 percent in 2013. The average PTE scores were higher than those of the TE scores of Islamic Banking sector in Bahrain for the same period.

Table 4: TE for Bahraini Islamic Banks (2010-2013)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	Mean	Standard Deviation
DMU1	1.00	1.00	0.69	0.66	0.84	0.188
DMU2	1.00	0.28	1.00	1.00	0.82	0.360
DMU3	0.47	0.71	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.256
DMU4	0.95	0.75	1.00	0.80	0.88	0.119
DMU5	0.57	0.66	0.39	0.32	0.49	0.157
DMU6	1.00	1.00	0.73	0.84	0.89	0.132
Mean	0.83	0.73	0.80	0.77	0.78	0.20
Standard Deviation	0.24	0.27	0.25	0.26	0.15	

Table 5: PTE for Bahraini Islamic Banks (2010-2013)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	Mean	Standard Deviation
DMU1	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.000
DMU2	1.00	0.58	1.00	1.00	0.90	0.210
DMU3	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.000
DMU4	1.00	0.88	1.00	1.00	0.97	0.060
DMU5	1.00	1.00	0.62	1.00	0.91	0.190
DMU6	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.000
Mean	1.00	0.91	0.94	1.00	0.96	0.08
Standard Deviation	0.00	0.17	0.16	0.00	0.05	

In measuring the SE of DMUs, the VRS assumption is used wherein there is a disproportional change in output compared with any change in inputs. As shown in Table 6, the number of pure SE Islamic banks was three in 2010 and 2012 and 2 in 2011 and 2013. The mean SE score was 83 percent in 2010 but dropped to 78 percent in 2011 and increased to 84 percent in 2012 but dropped to 77 percent in 2013. The DMUs showed a high dispersion in terms of SE scores as

evidenced by the average SE scores presented high standard deviations. The high dispersion in SE of DMUs may be due to the dispersion in input/output configuration and the size of operations.

Table 6: SE for Bahraini Islamic Banks (2010-2013)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	Mean	Standard Deviation
DMU1	1.00	1.00	0.69	0.66	0.84	0.188
DMU2	1.00	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.87	0.255
DMU3	0.47	0.71	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.256
DMU4	0.95	0.84	1.00	0.80	0.90	0.093
DMU5	0.57	0.66	0.63	0.32	0.55	0.155
DMU6	1.00	1.00	0.73	0.84	0.89	0.132
Mean	0.83	0.78	0.84	0.77	0.81	0.18
Standard Deviation	0.24	0.20	0.18	0.26	0.13	

Areas for Efficiency Improvement and Efficiency Reference Set

DMUs strive to operate at most productive scale size i.e., with CRS, in order to minimize costs and maximize revenue. In the short run, DMUs may operate in the zone of (IRS) or (DRS). However, in the long run, they will move towards CRS by becoming larger or smaller to survive in the competitive market.

The move towards efficient operations could involve scaling up or scaling down of size based on efficiency of a hypothetical best-practice composite reference unit. DEA constructs a hypothetical composite unit based on all units in the reference group. The input consumed by a DMU that can be reduced to a certain level without worsening output is known as slack. A hypothetical best-practice composite reference unit is made up of a subset of units that should be emulated by a given inefficient DMU in order to improve the efficiency of its operation. It identifies inputs that have to be reduced and outputs that need to be increased in order to make a particular DMU efficient. This information may help decision makers to determine whether the size of representative DMU in the particular industry is appropriate or not (Kumar and Gulati, 2008).

The ranges of improvements (in Million BDs) needed for DMUs inputs and outputs to reach TE efficiency are documented in Tables 7-9 (based on the CRS assumption with input orientation). Table 7 shows areas of improvements in 2010 for inefficient banks, viz. DMU3, DMU4, and DMU5 whereas the rest of DMUs are efficient and, therefore, require no changes in their inputs and outputs. The reference DMU for each of DMU3 and DMU4 is DMU1 and the reference for DMU5 is DMU6.

Table 7 also shows that the efficiency of DMU3 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 935.6 to 417.137 (a slack of 518.463), decreasing total owner's equity from 100.6 to 47.727, and increasing net profit from 0.226 to 0.242. The efficiency of DMU4 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 2543.7 to 2050.722, decreasing total owner's equity from 247.5 to 234.633, and increasing net profit from 0.3 to 1.192. The efficiency of DMU5 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 419.2 to 239.187 and decreasing total owner's equity from 118.1 to 59.557 and increasing net profit from 0.037 to 3.084.

Table 7: Areas for Efficiency Improvement and Reference Set in 2010 (Million BDs)

	Total Assets	Total Owner's Equity	Total Operating Income	Adjusted Net Profit (Loss)	Reference DMU
DMU1	5987 to 5987	685 to 685	248.3 to 248.3	3.479 to 3.479	DMU1
DMU2	856.6 to 856.6	201.9 to 201.9	22.4 to 22.4	14.662 to 14.662	DMU2
DMU3	935.6 to 417.137	100.6 to 47.727	17.3 to 17.3	0.226 to 0.242	DMU1
DMU4	2543.7 to 2050.722	247.5 to 234.633	85.05 to 85.05	0.3 to 1.192	DMU1
DMU5	419.2 to 239.187	118.1 to 59.557	12.5 to 12.5	0.037 to 3.084	DMU6
DMU6	1446.6 to 1446.6	360.2 to 360.2	75.6 to 75.6	18.653 to 18.653	DMU6

Areas of improvements in 2011 for inefficient banks are shown in Table 8. DMU2, DMU3, DMU4, and DMU5 are inefficient whereas DMU1 and DMU6 are efficient and, therefore, require no changes in their inputs and outputs. The reference for each of DMU2, DMU3, and DMU4 is the set of DMU 1 and DMU6 whereas the reference for DMU5 is DMU6.

It can be also found from Table 8 that the efficiency of DMU2 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 923.9 to 260.16, decreasing total owner's equity from 200.6 to 56.48, and increasing net profit from 0.99 to 2.7. The efficiency of DMU3 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 839.1 to 593.31, decreasing total owner's equity from 101.3 to 71.62, and increasing net profit from 0.52 to 1.03. The efficiency of DMU4 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 2601.1 to 1522.6 and decreasing total owner's equity from 217.4 to 162.3. The efficiency of DMU5 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 447.5 to 293.5 and decreasing total owner's equity from 118.9 to 71.19 and increasing net profit from 1.05 to 3.7.

Table 8: Areas for Efficiency Improvement and Reference Set in 2011 (Million BDs)

	Total Assets	Total Owner's Equity	Total Operating Income	Net Profit (Loss)	Reference DMUs
DMU1	6468 to 6468	678.4 to 678.4	279.4 to 279.4	1.99 to 1.99	DMU1
DMU2	923.9 to 260.16	200.6 to 56.48	12.7 to 12.7	0.99 to 2.7	DMU1,6
DMU3	839.1 to 593.31	101.3 to 71.62	26.1 to 26.1	0.52 to 1.03	DMU1,6
DMU4	2601.1 to 1522.6	217.4 to 162.3	65.9 to 65.9	0.7 to 0.7	DMU1,6
DMU5	447.5 to 293.5	118.9 to 71.19	14.7 to 14.7	1.05 to 3.7	DMU6
DMU6	1537.3 to 1537.3	372.9 to 372.9	77 to 77	19.48 to 19.5	DMU6

Table 9 compiles areas of improvements in 2012 for inefficient banks, viz. DMU1, DMU5, and DMU6 whereas DMU2, DMU3, and DMU4 are efficient and require no changes in their inputs and outputs. The reference for DMU1 is the set of DMU3 and DMU4, whereas the reference for DMU5 is the set of DMU2 and DMU3, and for DMU6 is the set of DMU2 and DMU4.

Table 9: Areas for Efficiency Improvement and Reference Set in 2012 (Million BDs)

	Total Assets	Total Owner's Equity	Total Operating Income	Net Profit (Loss)	Reference DMUs
DMU1	534.7 to 534.7	63.6 to 43.7	15.4 to 17.03	0.1 to 0.1	DMU3,4
DMU2	942 to 942	208.1 to 208.1	23.1 to 23.1	20.9 to 20.9	DMU2
DMU3	832.8 to 832.8	69.7 to 69.7	24.4 to 24.4	0.9 to 0.9	DMU3
DMU4	2724.1 to 2724.1	222.1 to 222.1	87.5 to 87.5	0.25 to 0.25	DMU4
DMU5	473.1 to 473.1	119.4 to 46.17	10.6 to 13.6	1.5 to 1.5	DMU2,3
DMU6	1437 to 2064.3	381.8 to 278.5	60.3 to 60.3	17.6 to 17.6	DMU2,4

Table 9 also shows that the efficiency of DMU1 can be improved by decreasing total owner's equity from 63.6 to 43.7. The efficiency of DMU5 can be improved by decreasing total owner's equity from 119.4 to 46.17. The efficiency of DMU6 can be improved by increasing total assets from 1437 to 2064.3 and decreasing total owner's equity from 381.8 to 278.5.

Table 10 documents areas of improvements in 2013 for inefficient banks, viz. DMU1, DMU4, DMU5, and DMU6 are inefficient whereas DMU2 and DMU3 are efficient and, therefore, require no changes in their inputs and outputs. The reference for each of DMU1, DMU4, DMU5, and DMU6 is DMU3.

Table 10 also shows that the efficiency of DMU1 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 614.9 to 404.533, decreasing total owner's equity from 62.1 to 34.711, and increasing net profit from 0.69 to 5.516. The efficiency of DMU4 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 2790.9 to 1857.4, decreasing total owner's equity from 200.4 to 159.375, and increasing net profit from 1.03 to 25.324. The efficiency of DMU5 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 542.2 to 172.667 and decreasing total owner's equity from 100.01 to 14.816 and increasing net profit by 0.66 to 2.354. The efficiency of DMU6 can be improved by decreasing total assets from 1565 to 1309.8 and decreasing total owner's equity from 367.7 to 112.388 and increasing net profit from 11.8 to 17.858.

Table 10: Areas for Efficiency Improvement and Reference Set in 2013 (Million BDs)

	Total Assets	Total Owner's Equity	Total Operating Income	Net Profit (Loss)	Reference DMU
DMU1	614.9 to 404.5	62.1 to 34.7	16.4 to 16.4	0.69 to 5.51	DMU3
DMU2	1088 to 1088	246.1 to 246.1	26.1 to 26.1	25.2 to 25.2	DMU2
DMU3	910.2 to 910.2	78.1 to 78.1	36.9 to 36.9	12.4 to 12.4	DMU3
DMU4	2790.9 to 1857.4	200.4 to 159.4	75.3 to 75.3	1.03 to 25.3	DMU3
DMU5	542.2 to 172.7	100.01 to 14.8	7 to 7	0.66 to 2.4	DMU3
DMU6	1565 to 1309.8	367.7 to 112.4	53.1 to 53.1	11.8 to 17.9	DMU3

Concluding Remarks

The DEA model provides a useful insight into measurement of efficiency of Islamic banks in Bahrain over time. During the sampled period 2010-2013, half of the Islamic banks were relatively efficient in managing their financial resources in 2010 and 2012, and two thirds were inefficient in 2011 and 2013. The mean efficiency indicated a negative change in 2011 compared to 2010 and in 2013 compared to 2012. One bank (DMU5) has consistently been relatively inefficient compared to its peers over the period 2010-2013.

The empirical results showed that three banks as per TE, six banks as per PTE and three banks as per SE were relatively efficient in 2010. In 2011, the results showed that two banks as per TE, four banks as per PTE and two banks as per SE were relatively efficient. In 2012, the results showed that three banks as per TE, five banks as per PTE and three banks as per SE were relatively efficient. The results also showed that in 2013, two banks as per TE, six banks as per PTE and two banks as per SE were relatively efficient.

The main contribution of this study is to provide management with information with regards to input and output improvements needed to reach optimal efficiency scores. It also provides information to relatively best practice banks in the composite set in the Kingdom of Bahrain as financial capital of the Middle East with its most diversified economy in the region and locate the relatively inefficient banks by comparison with the best practice ones.

Based on the findings of the study, it can be suggested for inefficient Bahraini Islamic banks that look into the option of reducing their total assets and total owner's equity while net profits are augmented in order to catch the relative efficiency level of their competitors. At a later stage, an advanced test might be conducted for a longer period to accurately specify the relatively inefficient DMUs.

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